

POLITICAL SCIENCES

MAIN GLOBAL TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN INVESTMENT MARKET

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Abstract

The article examines the main global trends in the development of the green investment market, including key success factors, risks associated with investing in green projects, as well as various industries in which green investments are actively developing. The authors of the article note an increase in demand for green bonds, venture capital, green funds and ETFs, as well as increased regulation by government agencies. The findings of the article show that green investments are a promising and growing market that has great potential for development and attracting investment. However, to successfully invest in green projects, it is necessary to take into account not only environmental aspects, but also financial and market conditions.

Keywords: green investments, ESG principles, ecology, green economy, green bonds, venture capital, climate funds, renewable energy, green obligations, circular economy, green technology innovations, sustainability, green start-ups.

Currently, the problems of climate change and environmental sustainability have become one of the main challenges for the world community. In this regard, more and more attention is being paid to green technologies and projects that can reduce the carbon footprint and improve the environment. In this regard, the development of the green investment market is becoming increasingly relevant. This scientific article examines the main global trends in the development of the green investment market, their features and prospects, and also evaluates the contribution of such investments to economic and environmental growth.

The green investment market is a branch of the financial industry that focuses on investing in companies, projects and products that have a positive impact on the environment and climate. The main development trend of this market includes multiple aspects. One of them, which is also one of the most imposing, is the aspect of the fast growth. The green investment market is growing at a rapid pace, and one of the reasons for this growth is the increasing number of companies that are going green and adopting a more environmentally responsible approach to business. Data from the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) shows that in 2022, global renewable energy capacity reached an all-time high of 3382 gigawatts (GW). This is an increase of 292 GW from 2021, marking the most significant yearly growth on record [1].

Another indicator of the rapid growth of the green investment market is the increasing number of investors who pay attention to environmental and social criteria when choosing their investments. Individual investor interest in sustainability is on the rise, according to survey findings in a new "Sustainable Signals" report by the Morgan Stanley Institute for Sustainable Investing and Morgan Stanley Wealth Management (2024). More than three quarters (77%) of individual investors globally say they are interested in investing in companies or funds that aim to achieve market-rate financial returns while also considering positive social and/or environmental impact. In addition, more than half (57%) say their interest has increased in the last two years,

while 54% say they anticipate boosting allocations to sustainable investments in the next year [2].

Assessing the trends, it is worth noting that the first issue of green bonds in 2007 was in the amount of 807.2 million US dollars. And by December 31, 2022, the total volume of green financial transactions reached US\$1.6 trillion. The intervention of the COVID-19 pandemic, despite forecasts, contributed to the growth of green and social bonds, which are used to raise capital for environmental and social projects [3].

Financial instruments of "green investments" are developing and expanding. According to the report "Global Trends in Renewable Energy Investment 2022" from the Frankfurt School-UNEP Collaborating Center for Climate & Sustainable Energy Finance, the Energy investment has been raised by 8% in 2022. World energy investment is raised by over 8% in 2022 and is also expected to reach a total of US\$2.4trn [3]. This increment in investment has been witnessed in all kinds of energy sectors, but the main boost existed in the power sector. The caveat is almost half the increase in capital spending is linked to higher costs. The majority of green investments in 2020 were aimed at developing renewable energy, especially solar and wind power.

In November 2023, the Global Sustainable Investment Alliance (GSIA) published the sixth edition of the biennial Global Sustainable Investment Review (GSIR), finding that US\$30.3 trillion is invested in sustainable assets globally. The report shows that in non-US markets – Canada, Europe, Japan, Australia and New Zealand – there has been a 20% increase in sustainable assets under management (AUM) since the 2020 GSIR [4].

In today's world, there are many green investment vehicles that are designed to invest in companies and projects that benefit the environment. Among them are green bonds, green funds, green indices, green loans and others. Green bonds are bonds whose proceeds are used to finance projects aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing energy efficiency and other environmental goals. According to S&P Global, Green bond issuance during the first half of 2023 reached

\$310 billion, marking the highest half-year total since the inception of the green bond market. Green bonds have comprised 59% of the GSSSB market in 2023 so far [5]. Nonfinancial corporates are currently the largest issuers of green bonds, despite issuance contracting 6% compared with the first half of 2022.

Financial institutions issued green bonds totaling \$135 billion in 2022, with 33% of them issued in China and Germany [6]. These fixed-income financial tools are specifically issued to raise funds for and support projects in environmentally friendly sectors such as renewable energy, clean transportation, waste management, and water conservation. Over the past decade, the issuance of green bonds has experienced a remarkable surge, with a staggering value of nearly 500 billion U.S. dollars worldwide in 2022 alone. This exponential growth underscores the increasing importance of green bonds as a pivotal instrument for mitigating the impacts of climate change and fostering sustainable development.

Typically, green investments are carried out mainly by developed countries, but recently more and more developing countries are joining this movement. For example, the number of developing countries issuing green bonds is increasing every year. In 2022, 73% of the total green bonds were issued by developed countries, while 21% were issued by developing countries, and the remaining 4% were held by supranational issuers [7]. According to experts, by 2025 the green bond market will reach \$1 trillion.

Green funds are investment funds that allocate funds to companies that produce environmentally friendly goods or provide environmentally friendly services. Green indices are indices that reflect the investment performance of companies engaged in the production of green goods or green services. They allow investors to gain access to companies working to benefit the environment. For example, the MSCI ACWI Low Carbon Target Index includes companies that are working to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

According to the report "Global Trends in Renewable Energy Investment" (2021), in 2020, investments in the renewable energy sector in the United States and Europe reached historical highs. In Europe, investments amounted to \$66.2 billion, which is 15% higher than the results of 2019. In the United States, investments in renewable energy amounted to \$55.5 billion, which is also a record figure [8]. There has been an increase in green bond volumes in recent years. According to the Green Bond Market Summary (2021), green bond issuance reached \$305 billion in 2020, a record high. Green bond volumes are expected to continue to grow in the coming years.

One of the most important international acts regulating the green investments market is the Paris Agreement, signed in 2015. It includes countries' commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and encourages the development of green technologies. The Paris Agreement created the Climate Risk Disclosure (TCFD) Initiative, which sets standards for disclosure of climate risks and options for managing them. In addition, the European Union adopted the Europe 2020 plan, which aims to make the EU economy more

"green" and sustainable. As part of this plan, the so-called Green Deal was created, under which the EU plans to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 [9].

Another example is the adoption and implementation of regulations aimed at stimulating green investments. In 2019, the European Union adopted a regulatory act known as the "Taxonomy Regulation", which defines criteria and definitions for green investments. This act aims to combat green money laundering and ensures standardization in this area. In February 2023, the European Commission approved a new action plan for the implementation of the European Green Deal (EU Green Deal), aimed at increasing Europe's competitiveness, accelerating the achievement of climate neutrality and creating an enabling environment for enhancing the EU's ability to develop technologies and products with a zero-carbon footprint. Similar regulations have been passed in other countries such as China and Japan.

The top leader according to the Green Future Index 2023 in its performance of economies with a huge focus on green investment is Iceland taking 6.69 score while Finland holds the 2nd position [10]. As a matter of fact, the Finnish government has transferred five million euros to the Green Recovery program of the Northern Environmental Finance Corporation (NEFCO), designed to contribute to the restoration of Ukraine taking into account climate change. The Green Recovery Program provides funding and technical assistance to local Ukrainian authorities to implement projects that contribute to post-war reconstruction and solving the humanitarian crisis on the way to a more sustainable green transition. The program started in July 2022, and its first donors were the EU, Denmark, Norway, Sweden and Finland [11]. The Finnish circular Economy program "New Direction", approved in 2021, is a strategic program to promote the circular economy and achieve systemic changes in it. The stated goal that the Finns intend to achieve by 2035 is to create a new efficient economy based on the principles of a waste-free economy. One of their main steps towards achieving the goal is a huge amount of investments they are about to make in 2024 – 6-9 billion EUR [12].

We also can't stand mentioning the 3rd rank country according to the Green Future Index 2023 which is Norway. Norway's climate finance totaled NOK 15.5 billion in 2022, partly through mobilization of a high level of private capital. At the UN Climate Change Conference (COP26) in Glasgow in 2021, Norway pledged to double its annual climate finance from NOK 7 billion in 2020 to NOK 14 billion by the end of 2026 [13]. This target is part of the broader commitment made by wealthy countries to mobilise USD 100 billion in climate finance annually from 2020. Mobilisation of private capital by Norfund accounted for a large share of the increase in Norwegian climate finance in 2022. The Climate Investment Fund alone mobilized more than NOK 5.6 billion in private capital. The purpose of the Climate Investment Fund is to help reduce or avoid greenhouse gas emissions by investing in renewable energy in developing countries.

In December 2023, the Danish government announced a decision to gradually introduce a "green" tax on air tickets from 2025, designed to compensate for the harm of air travel to the environment. The tax on passenger air transportation in Denmark will be introduced in stages from 2025 to 2030, during which it will grow from 70 Danish kroner (9.4 euros) to 100 kroner (13.4 euros) [14]. These are the average values, and the actual amount of tax is determined by the duration of the flight. The funds from the "green tax", among other things, will be used to finance the transition of Danish domestic aviation to environmentally friendly technologies. All of the above mentioned facts actually prove the current trends to proceed globally, and in the countries of Northern Europe predominantly.

China is currently the world's largest emitter of greenhouse gases, accounting for nearly 1/3 of the global total. Beijing is well aware of the effect its emissions have on climate change and has pledged to be carbon neutral by 2060, with emissions peaking in 2030. As part of its emissions reduction plan, China is introducing more eco-friendly practices in the financial services sector, but there is a steep learning curve, as loans to high-carbon industries account for a fairly high proportion of financial institutions' assets in the country. An accelerated withdrawal or delayed exit from high-carbon sectors may result in heightened financial risks. That said, there is a huge opportunity for sustainable finance in China given its ambitious emission reduction target. China's green finance market in the world's largest emitter nation has already reached US\$2.3 trillion, according to UBS.

Green bonds are an important part of the picture. According to S&P Global Market Intelligence, China issued the most green bonds globally in 2022 at US\$76.25 billion, according to data from Climate Bonds Initiative. This year, China is expected to issue between US\$90 billion and US\$100 billion in green bonds. Overall, Asia-Pacific countries issued US\$120.83 billion of green bonds in 2022, so China accounted for almost 2/3 of total issuance [15]. Data compiled by Bloomberg show that as of late 2022, China's green bond market had reached US\$300 billion in value. There were 1,029 entities made up of 1,029 bonds [16]. About 70% of that market is made up of local notes denominated in renminbi. To improve accessibility to global investors, the rest are mostly denominated in dollars.

Developing countries are also beginning to actively develop green technologies, which creates new opportunities for investors. According to a study by Ernst & Young, investors are increasingly targeting green investments that reduce their carbon footprint and improve environmental performance. In turn, this leads to increased investment in clean technologies and the development of new markets.

For example, the authorities of African states are increasingly declaring their commitment to ESG principles, while in their rhetoric, ESG transformation is primarily understood as environmental protection, the introduction of renewable energy sources (RES). It is important here to separate simple declarations of intent from real steps in this direction. According to Alexey

Tselunov, an independent expert on Africa, the countries of the Sahara-Sahel zone, such as Morocco, Egypt, Burkina Faso and Senegal, are successfully developing solar energy [17]. Kenya and Uganda are particularly attractive for investments in other renewable energy sources (RES): in the former, in particular, there are great prospects for the implementation of projects in geothermal energy. 22 countries of the continent use renewable energy sources in various forms as the main ones.

Egypt has done serious work to change the principles of the economy. In May 2022, the Egyptian Government published a national strategy on climate change until 2050, based on work in four areas: energy, transport, agriculture and water resources. The strategy, which will cost \$324 billion to implement, involves efforts to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, encourage the development and implementation of "green" technologies, and educate the public. Some of the projects are already being implemented: in cities there can be seen vehicles running on clean fuels, work is underway to create capacities for recycling garbage. It is Cairo that is called one of the main mouthpieces of the continent on the world stage on the issues of "green" transformation.

According to experts from the McKinsey & Company consulting group, Africa will need \$2 trillion for a "green" transition in the economy — an unthinkable amount for the poorest countries in the region. A possible way out is to rely on international support. In particular, China offers assistance in transforming the economies of African countries, which has been increasingly penetrating the continent in recent years.

In December 2021, the Eighth Ministerial Meeting of the China-Africa Cooperation Forum was held in Dakar, as a result of which the participants signed a joint declaration on climate. In it, Beijing promises to contribute in every possible way to the "green" transit of local economies, including by allocating funds for environmentally friendly projects and stopping the construction of coal plants. For example, since 2018, the Chinese company Dongfang Electric International Corporation has been helping Ethiopia to build the Aysha wind farm as part of the country's strategy to build a green economy. The installed capacity of the wind farm is 120 megawatts, and energy production is 467 gigawatt—hours per year. In addition to China, Europe, aimed at achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, can assist in the development of "green" energy in Africa. As part of the EU-African Union summit held in February 2022, it was decided to implement a large investment strategy Global Gateway. According to it, European states will invest \$150 billion in Africa, which will be directed, among other things, to the implementation of environmental transit and support for projects such as the Great Green Wall [18].

Thus, green investments are developing and expanding, and this is an important trend in the modern world of finance. The use of such tools helps investors not only earn money, but also contribute to environmental protection. Regulators around the world are developing and implementing strict rules for companies to comply with environmental regulations. This creates

additional opportunities for investors looking to invest in companies that are strict about their environmental footprint. In light of the increasing volumes of these investments, the global economy has seen increased regulation in this area. Regulations aimed at regulating and standardizing green investments are regularly adopted at the international and national levels.

The modern investment market is increasingly paying attention to the social responsibility of business and the environmental sustainability of companies. Investors, aware of their responsibility to society and the environment, are keen to invest in companies that are committed to environmental sustainability and social responsibility. This encourages companies to develop and implement more sustainable technologies, which helps create healthier and more prosperous environments for people to live in. Investors are increasingly using tools such as voting at shareholder meetings to increase influence over companies and force them to make more sustainable decisions. This allows investors to more actively influence companies and stimulate their development towards environmental sustainability and social responsibility.

In addition, green investments have significant social impact. They lead to the creation of new jobs, as well as an improvement in the quality of life in regions where green technologies are developed. According to the report "Green Jobs: Towards Decent Work in a Sustainable, Low-Carbon World" (2022), green investments can create up to 24 million jobs by 2030. This will have a significant social impact and contribute to the fight against poverty in developing countries. It is also worth noting that green investments are becoming more accessible to a wide audience of investors. There are a number of investment products, such as green bonds and investment funds, that provide the opportunity to invest in green projects and companies. This allows investors not only to make a profit, but also to contribute to the sustainable development of the economy.

As a result of a study of the main global trends in the development of the green investment market, we can conclude that this area is actively developing and becoming increasingly in demand in the light of climate change and environmental sustainability issues. The key factors for the success of green investments are support from government agencies, active participation of business and financial institutions, and growing consumer awareness of the need to switch to environmentally friendly technologies. However, it is also necessary to take into account the risks associated with investing in green projects, such as market instability, low liquidity and high costs. Overall, green investments are one of the key tools in the fight for environmental sustainability and contribute to the growth of the economy as a whole. It is also worth noting that green investments are not limited only to energy projects, but also include other sectors such as transport, agriculture, forestry, construction and others. Moreover, green investments can have not only an environmental but also a social component, for example, including projects to combat poverty and inequality.

Among the main global trends in the development of the green investment market are the growing demand for green bonds, investments in venture capital for startups in green industries, the development of the market for green funds and ETFs, as well as increased regulation by government agencies. Thus, green investments represent a promising and growing market that has great potential for development and attracting investment. However, to successfully invest in green projects, it is necessary to take into account not only environmental aspects, but also financial and market conditions.

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